

Isotropic to Directional Transport Cross Section Rehomogenization Procedure during the Nodal Diffusion Solution

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ABSTRACT

The transport cross section is important for obtaining accurate solution with nodal diffusion solvers. With interest in group constant generation in Monte Carlo (MC) codes on the rise, the question of how to generate transport cross section using MC becomes important. Traditionally, the Flux Separability Approximation (FSA) is used for MC, due to its guaranteed evaluation of the transport cross section. However, this approximation is well known to lead to erroneous solutions, requiring the use of alternative methods of generating the transport cross section. One such recent method is the Cumulative Migration Method, which can generate directional transport cross sections but is limited to an infinite lattice. Another method is direct neutron current weighting, which in principle cannot be used for generating the transport cross section in a single assembly model due to the production of a zero net current. Therefore, this direct approach can only be applied in multi-assembly colorsets, but this can be rather unpractical for the standard two-stage approach with branch-off analyses. As such, this paper proposes a rehomogenization technique that combines the traditional method generating the transport cross section, with neutron current weighting rehomogenization step applied directly within the nodal diffusion solution. The results of this rehomogenization procedure show general improvements over the isotropic transport cross section.

Keywords: Transport Cross Section, Rehomogenization, Nodal Diffusion

1. INTRODUCTION

In obtaining the solution from diffusion codes the transport cross section is of uttermost importance. However, there is no exact definition of the transport cross section for energy-dependent solutions. As a result, over the years the transport cross section has been approximated in many ways. In Monte Carlo (MC) codes, such as Serpent [1], OpenMC [2], MCNP [3], and Shift [4], up until recently it was common to rely on the out-scattering approximation [5] in tandem with the flux separability approximation (FSA) [6]. While these approximations are useful for MC codes to obtain the transport cross section, they are widely known to be inaccurate [7,8]. As such a consistent approach to generating cross sections, as is possible with deterministic codes [9], would greatly improve results.

Ideally, a method for generating the transport cross section should rely on an in-scattering current weighting approach. One such approach that aims to create a consistent transport cross section, is the directional Cumulative Migration Method (CMM), in which the migration area is used to generate a diffusion coefficient (and thus the transport cross section) [10]. However, the CMM can only be applied in infinite geometries; thus producing an isotropic value if the assembly is symmetric. In reality, however, the transport of neutrons will depend on the adjacent fuel assemblies and most likely be direction dependent.

In previous works it was demonstrated that it is in fact possible to directly obtain these current weighted transport cross sections for a colorset [11]. To generate these current weighted transport cross sections the moments of the total and in-scattering cross sections could be extracted using spherical harmonics from which the transport cross section could be calculated. However, such an approach is not suitable

for a typical two-step methodology with branch-off analyses, where group constants are first generated on infinite lattice using a transport code and then fed into an nodal diffusion solver such as DYN3D [12], and PARCS [13]. Therefore, the current work presents preliminary investigations into creating a direction-weighted transport cross section by generating lattice and fine-mesh cross sections and homogenizing these using a fine mesh nodal diffusion solution. This process of transitioning from fine-to-coarse group cross sections is denoted here as rehomogenization. The results obtained for the two colorset cases investigated here indicate that the method improves the prediction of the transport cross section and the subsequent multiplication factor and the group flux as well as power distributions.

2. METHODS TO OBTAIN THE TRANSPORT CROSS SECTION

2.1. A Single Fuel Assembly Model

To generate the transport cross section in an infinite lattice, one of the approaches relies on the in-scatter approximation in conjunction with the FSA. The in-scatter approximation takes the scattering kernel and integrates over the incoming energy to make a group. This yields that Σ_{tr}^g is function of the Σ_t , the scattering production kernel, $\Sigma_{sp1}(E' \rightarrow E)$, and the scalar flux, ϕ , as follows:

$$\Sigma_{tr}^g \approx \frac{\int_{E_g}^{E_{g-1}} [\Sigma_t(E)\phi(E) - \int_0^\infty \Sigma_{sp1}(E' \rightarrow E)\phi(E')dE']dE}{\int_{E_a}^{E_{g-1}} \phi(E)dE} \quad (1)$$

When applying the FSA, the spectrum of the scalar flux is used in lieu of the linear flux moments (the neutron current). As the scalar flux and current spectra can be different, such an approximation may yield inaccurate transport cross sections. The CMM method is a recently developed approach to generate the transport cross section without applying the flux separability approximation. CMM begins by acknowledging that the group-wise migration area, $(M_g^c)^2$, is the function of the cumulative diffusion coefficient, D_g^c , and the cumulative removal cross section, $\Sigma_{r,c}^g$, shown below [10].

$$(M_g^c)^2 = \frac{D_g^c}{\Sigma_{r,c}^g} \quad (2)$$

Then, to obtain the CMM group diffusion coefficient, D_g , a flux weighting scheme is used to unfold D_g^c given by [10]:

$$D_g^c = \frac{\sum_{g'=0}^g D_{g'}\phi_{g'}}{\sum_{g'=0}^g \phi_{g'}} \quad (3)$$

To compute Σ_{tr}^g from the CMM diffusion coefficient the definition of the diffusion coefficient can be used as follows:

$$\Sigma_{tr}^g = \frac{1}{3D_g} \quad (4)$$

Since all these definitions hold true the transport cross section calculated from this method can be stated to be equivalent to the current weighted in-scatter cross section [10]. However, since the calculation of the cumulative migration area requires the distance from birth to group removal, this method requires that the system being model is an infinite medium [10]. While the method shown here is for an isotropic transport cross section, CMM can be extended for directionality being equivalent to the current-weighting in-scatter approximation.

2.2. A Colorset Model

While CMM can be used to generate directional transport cross sections, it fails to capture the directionality that comes from neighboring lattices. To account for these neighboring effects, a simple

method is to calculate the transport cross section on a colorset. Additionally, since it is trivial to generate a colorset that guarantees that each lattice has a nonzero current, the in-scatter current weighting can be used and is given by:

$$\Sigma_{tr,u}^g = \frac{\int_{E_g}^{E_{g-1}} [\Sigma_t(E)J_u(E) - \int_0^\infty \Sigma_{sp1}(E' \rightarrow E)J_u(E')dE']dE}{\int_{E_g}^{E_{g-1}} J_u(E)dE} \quad (5)$$

The exact method of how to tally with the current is given in Ref [11]. However, when applied to the traditional two-stage approach, generating cross sections on these colorsets can become problematic/unpractical. As such, a technique that would allow for the generation of the transport cross section and then account for effects of the neighbors would be ideal. It should also be noted that due to the directionality of the transport cross section found from this approach is solely due to the currents being different for each direction.

3. REHOMOGENIZATION CORRECTION TECHNIQUE

Recently a method to rehomogenize group constants has been reported and demonstrated on 3D cores. The main idea of the method is to correct infinite group constants by accounting for neighboring effects [13,14]. The method relies on generating group constants using an infinite lattice model, in which the assembly is subdivided to fine meshes (i.e., submeshed) in addition to generating these group constants for the entire fuel assembly (i.e., standard lattice cross sections). Then, these fine and coarse group constants are used by the nodal solver to obtain corrected lattice cross sections.

The following steps are included in the reported methodology:

- Perform lattice calculations for each fuel assembly by applying reflective boundary conditions.
 - In this stage, fuel assemblies are explicitly modeled (Fig. 1a) to generate macroscopic cross sections and discontinuity factors (DFs).
 - These cross sections and DFs are generated for the entirety of the fuel assembly (denoted here as the coarse mesh and shown in Fig. 1b) and on the sub-assembly level (denoted here as fine mesh as seen in Fig. 1c).
 - The coarse mesh cross sections and DFs are represented by Σ^{Lat} and df^{Lat} respectively, while for the fine mesh, Σ_i^{Lat} and df_i^{Lat} are used.

Figure 1. Illustration of the coarse and fine homogenized meshes.

- The nodal diffusion solver uses the pre-generated fine mesh cross sections and DFs to obtain the solution for the entire core (or the modeled system as seen in Figure 2 that presents an arbitrary core). In our study, only a 2-dim solution was obtained.

Figure 2. Illustration of the core solution using fine meshes. An arbitrary example with six different fuel assemblies each containing a different set of fine group cross sections and DFs.

- The fluxes obtained for all the fine meshes (i.e., ϕ_i) are then used to create homogenized macroscopic cross sections for each fuel assembly using:

$$\Sigma^{2D} = \frac{\sum_{i \in K} \Sigma_i^{Lat} \phi_i V_i}{\sum_{i \in K} \phi_i V_i} \quad (6)$$

where, Σ^{2D} is calculated for each coarse fuel assembly using the fine mesh fluxes (ϕ_i) within that fuel assembly and the volumes (V_i) of the fine meshes (or the areas in our case). In Eq. 6 K represents a specific fuel assembly and i denotes the fine mesh region.

- Similarly, the nodal diffusion solver is also applied to obtain the flux distribution within each fuel assembly (Fig. 1c) using reflective boundary conditions on the fine mesh. This solution is obtained for each fuel assembly separately. Eq. 6 is used to obtain the homogenized group cross sections and DFs. These values will be denoted as Σ^{SA} and df^{SA} , where SA stands for Single Assembly.
- Then, lattice corrected (i.e., Σ^{corr}) cross sections and discontinuity factors (i.e., df^{corr}) can be calculated using the following relations:

$$\begin{aligned} \Sigma^{corr} &= \Sigma^{Lat} + \Sigma^{2D} - \Sigma^{SA} \\ df^{corr} &= df^{Lat} + df^{2D} - df^{SA} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

- Finally, the corrected group constants are then used in the coarse mesh to obtain a solution.

It must be pointed out that in the current study the above rehomogenization approach did not have a significant impact on the results obtained with the non-corrected lattice values. Therefore, it was decided to complement the above methodology using directional transport cross sections obtained by having the volume (area in our case) averaged node neutron current in each respective direction, i.e., x and y ($J_{x,i}$ and $J_{y,i}$). These directional currents are known from applying the nodal expansion method.

To calculate the directional transport cross section, the above method is modified slightly. The 2D core solution using the submesh cross sections and reference discontinuity factors (calculated based on each individual fuel assembly model) allows for the calculation of the x- and y-wise currents on the submesh level. These currents within each assembly are then used to collapse the spatially dependent submesh isotropic transport cross sections using:

$$\Sigma_{tr}^x = \frac{\sum_i \Sigma_{tr,i} J_{x,i}}{\sum J_{x,i}} ; \Sigma_{tr}^y = \frac{\sum_i \Sigma_{tr,i} J_{y,i}}{\sum J_{y,i}} \quad (8)$$

Unique x- and y-transport cross sections are produced for each fuel assembly.

Lastly, it should be noted that work presented here is preliminary and as such the following are not thoroughly investigated:

- Spatial mesh sensitivities studies - the division of the assembly into multiple fine structures (e.g., 5-by-5 or 10-by-10).
- Energy condensation in conjunction with fine mesh - this refers to generating the fine mesh macroscopic cross sections with a finer energy grid (e.g., 8) and performing the fine mesh solution with this fine energy structure. Then, condensation to a coarser mesh (e.g., fuel assembly or quarter) and coarser energy grid (e.g., 2 group) within the rehomogenization step.
- Statistics – when generating the fine mesh cross section, it must be ensured that suitable number of neutron histories and cycles are used especially to capture the net currents for each submesh region as these are needed to calculate the reference discontinuity factors. In the current study, an extensive number of histories and cycles were used to avoid this potential error propagation issue.
- No submeshing was used for the reflector and as such the transport cross section calculated for the reflector is always isotropic. This is planned to be studied in the near future.

All the methods presented here were obtained by a Custom Educational Nodal Diffusion Tool (coreCend) developed by the Computational Reactor Engineering Group (CoRE) at Georgia Institute of Technology. This code is developed as an educational tool to provide educators and students with hands-on experience with using nodal diffusion solvers. coreCend relies on the nodal expansion method coupled with a Coarse mesh finite difference solver (CMFD). The code is hosted on the Georgia Institute of Technology GitHub repository <https://github.gatech.edu/dkotlyar6/CORE-CEND> that can be accessed only through the Georgia Tech resources at the moment.

4. RESULTS

In the current research two case studies are investigated: case 1, an all-fuel assembly colorset and case 2, a reflector-fuel colorset, shown in Figure 3. The fuel assemblies in both cases are submeshed in accordance to Figure 1c. In Figure 3 the enrichments of the blue pins are 4.55%, grey pins are 2.60%, navy pins are 4.05%, and the green pins are 4.55% and contain 8% of gadolinia.

Figure 3. 2-by-2 Reflected super-cell models.

Table I presents the results for both cases. In both cases it is shown that the directional transport cross section when calculated help improve the power predicted by the nodal diffusion solution, while the tallied transport cross section (which come from a colorset model) appears to be case dependent. This result for the tallied cross section is expected since the discontinuity factors are dependent on whether the diffusion is assumed isotropic or directional. Considering these results, the rest of this paper will focus on case 2.

Table I Relative differences in fluxes, power, and reactivity across all fuel assemblies.

	Fluxes			Power	
	$\Delta\rho$, pcm	Max, %	Av., %	Max, %	Av., %
Case 1					
Isotropic CMM xs	3	1.47	0.62	1.13	0.77
Tallied Directional transport xs	3	2.22	0.68	1.78	0.85
Calculated Directional transport xs	4	1.57	0.72	0.61	0.25
Case 2					
Isotropic CMM xs	241	1.52	0.77	1.27	0.89
Tallied Directional transport xs	183	1.76	0.74	1.06	0.74
Calculated Directional transport xs	211	1.20	0.55	0.95	0.62

Figure 4 shows the pin power distribution of the bottom left assembly for the reference, isotropic transport cross sections, and the calculated directional transport cross sections. It is clear from the figure that both the directional transport cross sections improve on the pin power distribution by flattening out the power difference. However, the transport cross section appears to have little effect on the corners, which are highly dependent on the approximation from the nodal solution.

Figure 4. Comparison of intranodal power distribution for the Gadolinia-based fuel assemblies.

Lastly, Table II shows the diffusion coefficients for case 2. While there is no error estimation on the calculated diffusion coefficients, the relative error in the fine mesh never exceeded 0.03%. From which it is observed that the calculated directional diffusion coefficients, in general, were found to be bound by the tallied directional diffusion coefficients and the isotropic diffusion coefficients. Another point of interest is that the calculated diffusion coefficients appear to have not gained as much directionality as expected, in particular the upper left region where the neighbors are identical. This may be an artifact of the submesh used and or the coarse groups used. As such it is important that these two aspects are further investigated in the future.

Table II Fast (i.e., 1) and thermal (i.e., 2) diffusion coefficients in x - and y -directions in cm.

	Isotropic	Tallied	Calculated
Upper left corner (no poison)	$D_{1,2}^{x,y} = 1.384, 0.407$	$D_{1,2}^x = 1.480, 0.257$ $D_{1,2}^y = 1.671, 0.380$	$D_{1,2}^x = 1.460, 0.373$ $D_{1,2}^y = 1.459, 0.384$
Bottom left corner (with poison)	$D_{1,2}^{x,y} = 1.391, 0.406$	$D_{1,2}^x = 1.488, 0.230$ $D_{1,2}^y = 1.489, 0.237$	$D_{1,2}^x = 1.468, 0.478$ $D_{1,2}^y = 1.468, 0.478$
Upper right corner (Reflector)	$D_{1,2}^{x,y} = 1.983, 0.341$	$D_{1,2}^x = 1.113, 0.331$ $D_{1,2}^y = 1.112, 0.331$	$D_{1,2}^x = 1.983, 0.341$ $D_{1,2}^y = 1.983, 0.341$

5. CONCLUSIONS

The treatment of the transport cross section is crucial for obtaining accurate results using diffusion. With modern computing architecture interest in generating group constantly using Monte Carlo has increased. Traditionally Monte Carlo codes used the out-scatter approximation along with the Flux Separability Approximation to generate an isotropic transport cross section. However, it is well known that the transport cross section generated in this method can lead to erroneous results. To mitigate these issues, the Cumulative Migration Method (CMM) was developed and extended for directionality. However, the CMM is limited to an infinite lattice and thus cannot account for the effect on the neighbors. Another method that does account for the effect of the neighbors is to use in-scatter current weighted approach, but this method poses difficulty when applied to the traditional two stage approach. As such, a workflow where the transport cross section is generated with a more traditional approach and then rehomogenized with the current is presented here. The results of recalculating the transport cross section through rehomogenization show general improvement from their isotropic counterparts. However, when compared to their tallied counterparts their directionality was found to be minimal. This oddity from what is expected should be further investigated with sensitivity studies on the submesh and energy structure.

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